

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Hasyim, La Ode M., Prakoso, Lukman Yudho, and Risman, Helda. (2021), *Perang Semesta (Total War) Strategy for Preventing Terrorism Act (Study in Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport)*. In: *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, Vol.4, No.2, 76-86.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.04.02.277

The online version of this article can be found at:
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Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Perang Semesta (Total War) Strategy for Preventing Terrorism Act (Study in Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport)

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Abstract

Total war is involving all national components such as citizens, territories and national resources in order to defend territorial integrity, sovereignty, and national security from any threats. One of these threats is the act of terrorism which endangers the unity, sovereignty and security of the nation. Acts of terrorism are carried out to create a terror with ideological, political and religious motives and are carried out in vital objects of the state, the environment, and public facilities. One of the vital objects of a country that is prone to acts of terrorism is an airport, which is a place for various activities such as the movement of aircraft, people and goods. Moreover, an airport is a very important infrastructure in supporting the national defense. In this study, the researcher took Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport, Makassar, as the research site considering that several large cases of terrorism and radicalism have occurred in the South Sulawesi region. The objective of this study is to analyze the total war strategy carried out in the Sultan Hasanuddin Airport area as an effort to prevent acts of terrorism at the airport as a vital national object. The research method used is qualitative. The data have been collected from interviews, observations and literature study. The results of this research are in preventing terrorism, a total war strategy that is implemented has three components, including the 'ends,' which could prevent the acts of terrorism in Sultan Hasanuddin Airport and strengthen the national defense. The 'means' which is manifested in all national components, both government and private agencies, military, police and civil society, as well as facilities and infrastructure. The 'ways' which is the intelligence operations, strengthening cooperation between the military and civilians, strengthening synergy between ministries / agencies, training, counseling, completing security tools to prevent acts of terrorism.

Keywords: Airport, Prevention, Terrorism, Total War, Strategy

Introduction

Perang Semesta (Total War) consists of two syllables namely *perang* (war) and *semesta* (total/universe). War has several meanings according to the times. Previously, war was defined as a massive battle that took place between two countries / kingdoms aiming to expand territories, establish the colonies, spread the religion, or overthrow the legitimate government (Prabowo et al., 2016). However, after World War II ended and the cold war began, the concept of war began to change. The definition of war has more or less experienced a shift in meaning, where war is no longer just a big battle with weapons, but a large-scale conflict that disrupts the territorial integrity and sovereignty of the Republic of Indonesia, both from within and outside the country. This large-scale conflict is also not closed to armed conflict. Meanwhile, the word *semesta* literally means *seluruh* (whole), *segenap* (entire), *semuanya* (everything), and universal (Setiawan, 2019). It is a numeric word which expresses a very large and comprehensive number.

Therefore, from the meaning of these two words, the phrase *perang semesta* can be interpreted as a large-scale conflict either in the form of battle or in other forms, which disturbs the territorial integrity and sovereignty of a country, especially in this study, the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI). In its action, *perang semesta* (total war) involves all national components, namely all citizens, regions, and national resources (Prabowo et al., 2016). The form of disturbance other than armed conflict, whether ridden by foreign or domestic actors and carried out in all national aspects.

However, *perang semesta* is often equated with guerrilla warfare during the struggle against colonialism in Indonesia, where one of the similarities between universal war and guerrilla warfare is the involvement of all national components in the war. Even so, in this war the threats faced are not limited to the occupiers and armed actors who threaten the security of the Republic of Indonesia like guerrilla had done, but with a broader spectrum of threats and are not military threats.

These threats are greatly influenced by globalization that is currently happening throughout the world. According to the statement of the Minister of Defense, Prabowo Subianto, the threat is currently divided into three dimensions, the first is an unreal threat namely open warfare, the second is a real threat, and the last is a mindset threat. Of those three dimensions, the real threat dimension is realized and is known to be happening at this time, including (1) terrorism & radicalism, (2) natural disasters, (3) cyber & intelligence, (4) piracy & theft of natural resources, (5) drugs, (6) epidemics, (7) border problems, and (8) separatism / rebellion (Eksa, 2019).

Based on this statement, it is known that one of the real threats that is happening is terrorism and radicalism. In Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5 of 2018, terrorism is defined as an act that uses violence or threats of violence that cause mass casualties, and / or cause damage or destruction to strategic vital, the environment, public facilities, or international facilities with ideological, political, or security disturbance motives.

Before the terminology of terrorism has been widely known, acts of terror with a religious background had occurred in Indonesia. One of them was an airplane hijacking by Komando Jihad in 1977 (Nurdin, 2011). Nowadays, acts of terrorism have shifted in terms of objectives, targets, ways of raising funds, recruiting members, and communicating to spread radical-terrorism views. The globalization process that is currently taking place provides an opportunity for global terrorist organizations to develop. Terrorist organizations take advantage of the era of openness to obtain information and cooperate internally between one terrorist organization and another. In addition, the existing opportunities are also used to secure geographic access to financial support and weapons, so that globalization creates a change in the pattern of acts of terrorism itself.

One of the significant changes in the pattern is the target of the terrorist act itself. Previously, acts of terror were carried out at places related to certain religions, both places of worship and places where many non-Muslims gathered. However, currently the targets of terror are prioritizing areas where people gather, vital objects, public facilities, and the police.

Talking about vital objects as targets of terrorism, in the current era of globalization, the movement of the economic wheels of society which demands speed and timeliness, therefore air transportation services are a top priority in

the movement of people and goods. Airport is a strategic place for the development of threats with the argument that airports are one of the vital objects of the country where various activities are carried out, such as aircraft movement, hustle of people, and transport goods such as passenger baggage, cargo, and post, airports also have a role as infrastructure in supporting national defense, so that the possibility of airports being targeted by acts of terrorism is quite high, and if this occurs it will result in large losses both in material and non-material terms.

As mentioned earlier, before the terminology of terrorism was used, there was a terrorist act happened in Garuda DC-9 flight 209 of Jakarta-Medan flight route containing 48 passengers by 5 members of Komando Jihad on March 28, 1981. This action was thwarted by *Kopassanda* troops (now *Kopassus* – Special Forces Commando) with a military operation called "Operation Woyla." In this incident, 4 terrorists, 1 pilot, and 1 *Kopassanda* member died, and all the passengers on the plane survived.

After that, moving on from 2010 onwards, a bomb was set by Al-Shabaab Al-Mujahideen on February 3, 2016, in passenger plane in Somalia, and detonated shortly after take-off causing a hole in the plane. On 22 March 2016, two terrorists blew themselves up at the entrance to the international airport terminal in Brussels. On June 28, 2016 at Ataturk International Airport in Istanbul, Turkey, three terrorists opened fire at the departure terminal then detonated explosive vests, killing more than forty people and 150 others injured.

Based on data, there has been no recent act of terrorism in the airport area, although it cannot be neglected. Several reasons, namely, airports are symbolic targets of prosperity and mastery of technology because airports are places that have a high level of security. The acts of terror carried out at the airport will provide an international stage for the perpetrators, as well as the mastermind behind the terror attacks. In addition, the consequences for the state if acts of terror occur will greatly affect various national sectors such as politics, economics and international appeal. And most importantly, the security of Indonesia's territory and society itself is threatened.

One area that has a long history of terrorism is South Sulawesi, started 18 years ago. Bomb terror at the Kentucky Fried Chicken (KFC) motion on October 12, 2001, Mall Ratu Indah incident on December 5, 2002, bombing at the Samppodo Indah cafe on January 10, 2004, bomb-throwing targeting Former Governor Syahrul Yasim Limpo in November 2012 by network members Poso, up to the latest, the suicide bombing in the Philippines by a married couple from Makassar in January 2019 (Alsair, 2019). It seems that this makes the rank of South Sulawesi Province, especially Makassar City prone to the threat of terrorism. So it is possible that the terrorist networks are still latent or a lone-wolfs, there are still many of them spreaded and have not been detected.

Up to now, there have not been any recorded acts of terrorism in the airport area or in the aviation sector in the South Sulawesi region, although it cannot be neglected. Therefore, a research was carried out at one of the international airports, namely Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport in Makassar. From the results of observations and data obtained, the problems of security disturbances that often occur at Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport include the smuggling of weapons and ammunition, Narcotics, illegal Natural Resources, prone to breaching the guardrail to the side of the Air Base area, and various actions of legal violations that have the potential to occur in the working area of Sultan Hasanuddin Airport. Of course it will be very crucial if there is an airport hijacking, such as a self-detonation action, or a hijacking of an aircraft targeting the airbase, it will be very fatal for the security and defense aspects of Indonesia considering the proximity of the airport and the airbase, especially Air Base's missile storage warehouse for combat aircraft.

Therefore, to prevent acts of terrorism within Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport, a strategy is needed to be implemented to determine the objectives, facilities and infrastructure, as well as ways that can be done to maximize the efforts to be carried out through *perang semesta* (total war) strategy. As said by Lt. Gen. TNI (Ret.) Joko Suryo Prabowo, in dealing with acts of terrorism, so many components of the nation were involved besides that the activities and war operations carried out were also very complex, therefore acts of terrorism, both handling and prevention, use a universal war strategy. Prabowo et al., 2016).

Research Methodology

The researcher used a qualitative method in this research. According to Creswell, qualitative research is conducted with the aim of understanding a phenomenon based on the participant's point of view, so that researchers can identify problems directly, because they are involved in participant activities, or by investigating with a narrative approach, namely collecting stories from the individuals involved (Creswell, 2014).

Besides, the approach taken in this research is a case study limited to a narrow (micro) area, because it only focuses on phenomena that occur at the individual, group, or institutional level. The cases are also limited to certain types of cases, at certain places or loci, and within a certain time. Due to the narrow coverage area, case study research is not intended to draw general conclusions or derive generalizations. Therefore, this type of research does not require a population and a sample. This thesis only examines the cooperation made by related parties to prevent any terror threats that may occur in the Sultan Hasanuddin Airport area.

Strategi Perang Semesta (Total War Strategy)

Figure 1: Strategy Lykke Model

Source: Yarger, 2006, pages 107-113

In Figure 1, the model from Lykke provides a coherent form to strategy theory by depicting it with a strategy supported by three factors as a base including goals, means and mediums, as well as upholding national security on it. The model illustrates that $\text{Strategy} = \text{Goals} + \text{Means} + \text{Mediums}$. When those three base are unbalanced, it increases the risk of implementing this strategy. From Lykke's model above, Objectives are Goals, Concepts are ways to achieve goals and Resources are means to support the way things are done. The strategy is said to fail if those three are unbalanced which is caused by an imbalance of the legs that support the strategy and in the end will have a high-risk impact on national security.

Meanwhile, according to Joko Suryo Prabowo, *perang smesta* is a war (not only fighting with weapons) that has the aim of maintaining territorial integrity, upholding sovereignty, and realizing the safety of the nation from all threats by using all national components including citizens, territories and national resources. Furthermore, it is carried out in various ways, such as intelligence operations, diplomacy, and so on (Prabowo et al., 2016).

Figure 2: Illustration of *Perang Semesta*

Source: Prabowo et al., 2016, page 15

In Figure 2, it is explained that the scheme for conducting *perang semesta* requires many components with complex activities.

1. Overcoming conflict (armed).
2. Disturbing relations between opponents and the people.
3. Build relationships with the people.
4. Disturbing relations between opponents and the international community.
5. Build relationships with the international community.

Therefore, *perang semesta* strategy is a strategy that is established from the goals, methods and means, as well as upholding national security, where national security here is to prevent acts of terrorism that might occur in the area of Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport.

Prevention

Preventive action is an action taken with the aim of avoiding deviant behavior or crime (Syaiful, 2008). Prevention as an effort to tackle crime can be pursued by: (1) Application of criminal law; (2) prevention without crime; (3) influencing people's views on crime and punishment through the mass media (Arief, 2011).

Efforts to prevent a crime by means of the criminal justice system can be carried out with repressive and preventive measures. Repressive actions are all actions taken by law enforcement officials after the occurrence of a criminal act. This action can also be seen as prevention for the future as a special prevention, namely an effort to reduce the number of crimes by giving (criminal) penalties to the perpetrators of crimes and also trying to commit acts by remedying the behavior of the perpetrators who commit crimes, so that the frequency of crimes can be minimized (Rochmah, 2005).

Meanwhile, Preventive Measures are actions taken to prevent or guard against the possibility of a crime occurring. This preventive effort must be carried out systematically and regularly to prevent the crime from arising. Preventive action can be developed from various sources that also have the potential for preventive-effects, for example the press / mass media, the use of technological advances and the utilization of the potential preventive-effects of law enforcement officials such as raids / operations, educative communicative activities with the community, and so on (Arief, 2008).

Acts of Terrorism

Terrorism according to Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5 of 2018 concerning Amendments to Law Number 15 of 2003 concerning Stipulation of Government Regulations in Lieu of Law Number 1 of 2002

concerning the Eradication of Criminal Acts of Terrorism into Law, is an act that uses violence or threat of violence that creates an atmosphere of terror or widespread fear, which can cause mass casualties, and / or cause damage or destruction to vital strategic objects, the environment, public facilities, or international facilities with ideological, political or disturbing motives security.

Airport Security

In the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number PM 127 of 2015 and Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2009 concerning Aviation, it is stated that an airport is an area on land and / or waters with certain boundaries used as a place for aircraft to land and take off, boarding and disembarking of passengers, loading and unloading of goods, and places for intra and intermodal transfer of transportation, which are equipped with aviation safety and security facilities, as well as basic facilities and other supporting facilities.

Furthermore, in the Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 70 of 2001 concerning Airport in Chapter XII, article 51. In paragraph (1) it is stated that airports or air bases can be used jointly for civil aviation and military aviation. Furthermore, in paragraph (2), it is stated that the joint use of an airport or an air base as referred to in paragraph (1) shall be carried out by taking into account:

- a. Aviation security and safety;
- b. Smooth flight operations;
- c. Airbase security and defense;
- d. Civil and military aviation interests

As a vital national object, the security of the airport must be protected and maintained. Security is carried out by airport managers as stated in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2009 concerning Aviation Article 327 paragraph (1) which states that Airport Business Entities or Airport Operational Units are required to create, implement, evaluate and develop airport security programs. air at each airport guided by the security program.

Discussion and Result

In order to prevent acts of terrorism that occurred at Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport, a *perang semesta* strategy has been implemented. To implement this strategy, it is necessary to know the ends (objectives), means (medium, tools, resources), and ways that can optimize efforts to prevent acts of terror that may occur.

Potential Terrorism Threats at Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport

The potential threat of terrorism at Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport can come from two factors, namely internal and external factors.

- a. Internal factors could arise from within the institution itself.
 - a) Human Resources

Potential threats that come from HR are in the form of internal personnel, namely airport employees, airline employees, or other personnel who have been exposed to radical groups and ideologies, so that they are free to carry out their actions in the airport area, both acts of terror and supporting acts of terror.

- b) Equipment / Facilities

The equipment or facilities in question are those related to airport security factors. Some of the machines owned by Sultan Hasanuddin Airport are standard equipment that must be provided by an airport. Meanwhile, some other equipment is only mandatory for airports, such as scanning machines (X-Ray). In addition to monitoring the area, we still use CCTV as a surveillance tool and walking patrols. The drawback is that CCTV has the potential to be hijacked by hackers, while walking patrols by officers have a shortage in the number of personnel.

- b. External factors are originating from outside the institution and their existence has a direct effect on the security of Sultan Hasanuddin Airport.

a) Cargo

JBW Group International (Zaroni and Basri, 2016) states that there are 4 types of threats to cargo, namely Shrinkage and Theft, Terrorism, Goods Smuggling, and Piracy.

- 1) Shrinkage is a product loss that occurs between production or purchases from the supplier to the point of sale. The reason is that the item was stolen by an insider (employee), mal-administration, or fraud.
- 2) Terrorism activities often use cargo transportation services to send something that has the potential to disturb the security of an area. Another nuisance was an attack on the cargo itself by terrorists.
- 3) Smuggling of goods through cargo services. Smuggled goods can threaten the smooth flow of goods shipments and risk causing legal, financial, and even damage to the company's reputation. Various methods are used in smuggling goods, such as fake seals on shipping containers, fake damage to goods, hacking into logistics company or port information systems, preparing criminals to 'work' as employees in manufacturing companies, and logistics as well as exchanging legal goods for illegal goods, which has the same weight at the transit point. The criminals are constantly growing and getting more and more creative in using legal shipments to smuggle their illegal cargo.
- 4) Piracy is a problem that has increased. Hijackers are constantly changing their tactics, targets using the latest weapons, and using more sophisticated techniques. This is solely intended to increase the success ratio.

b) Passengers

Airline passengers and prospective passengers are important users of an airport. Its existence can be used as a measure of the success of the aviation business in which the airport is one of its parts.

c) Intruders

People who can enter the Limited Security Area are prospective passengers who have air transport documents, individuals, aircraft personnel, and employees / employees who have entry permits. Except for Public Areas, there are a series of procedures used to enter Limited Security Areas, Sterile Areas and Restricted Areas.

A person who does not have the requirements to enter the three regions but still enters them secretly can be categorized as an intruder. An intruder is a person who enters secretly and without permission for a specific purpose. Intruders who successfully break into the area have the potential to threaten flight security and safety.

The strategy of *Perang Semesta* in Preventing Terrorism at Sultan Hasanuddin Airport

Based on the strategic theory of the Lykke model, it has the outcome of maintaining national security, namely territorial integrity, as well as the nation's sovereignty and safety from all threats, where national security is supported by a strategy built from three things, namely ends, concepts (ways), and resources (means).

The goal of this strategy is to prevent acts of terrorism in the area of Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport, where the airport is in the same area as the Sultan Hasanuddin Air Base belonging to the Indonesian Air Force. In this case, it is clear that in order to achieve the objectives of this strategy, strong coordination is required of related institutions and agencies, not only law enforcement officials, as well as airport officers, but also military personnel, namely the Indonesian Air Force. If acts of terrorism occur, the danger that threatens is very great, apart from the possibility of hijacking aircraft or bombing the airport area, given the location of the ammunition warehouse belonging to the Indonesian Air Force is adjacent to the airport location so that more components need to be involved.

Meanwhile, means and ways can be determined based on the potential threat of terrorism in the Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport area.

Potential that comes from internal factors include:

a. Human Resource

Ways that can be carried out are mental coaching activities for human resources who are in the airport environment. Coaching is carried out by each agency such as airport managers, the police, and the Indonesian National Army, as well as the Regional Government in the framework of fortifying human resources from the influence of radicalism which can develop into acts of terror. Intelligence operations are also used to support this activity as early detection, in order to find out quickly and precisely about the development of radical understanding among human resources in the region.

Means used in making these efforts could be physical facilities and non-physical. Physical facilities can be done by providing guidance in the surrounding places of worship through utilizing trusted religious experts, while non-physical facilities can be in the form of policies that support these activities.

b. Facilities

Ways that can be done is updating the technology. The use of means in the form of CCTV placed on unexpected spots, face recognition tools, Handheld Explosive Trace Detector and xray security scanners that have the latest technology that has a high level of inspection speed and high accuracy will maximize the strategy implemented. Moreover, if the addition of cctv and face recognition is in parts that are very prone to terrorism attacks, such as in the area close to the missile storage warehouse belonging to Sultan Hasanuddin Lanud and the parking area. In addition to dealing with the hijacking carried out by terrorist actors at airport facilities, trainings are carried out to improve capabilities in the cyber field and the use of modern technology, both at local governments, airports, police, and the Indonesian National Army.

Potential that comes from external factors:

a. Society with radical views

Understanding of a teaching cannot be forced on someone, including ingrained radical understanding. Ways on this strategy in dealing with radical-minded people to prevent acts of terrorism at airports is counseling about the dangers of terrorism by local governments in collaboration with National Counter-Terrorism Agency (BNPT) and universities. The involvement of cleric in warding off radical teachings that have the potential to become acts of terror. Meanwhile, the means they have are the existence of cleric and traditional leaders whose influence is greater on the community than the policies owned by the local government.

b. Intruder

Ways in this strategy in dealing with the threat of terrorism from intruders is the need for increased security on ticket checking and passenger checking at check-in. The use of the latest technology such as face recognition, fingerprint scanning can be quite an effective way of dealing with intruders who pretend to be passengers. Meanwhile, the means that are needed are the alertness of airport security, police and local TNI personnel in an emergency. In addition to infiltrating as passengers, abandoned spots will also become big gaps for intruders in the airport area that could possibly be used to detonate bombs or cause chaos, so it is necessary to install a perimeter instruction detection system.

c. Airport Visitors

Visitors are not only those who will act as aircraft passengers, but anyone who can enter the airport area by passing through the security guard are also airport visitors. Ways that is carried out is of course still maintaining security by not reducing the level of suspicion on all people in the airport area. Of course

this is done based on means owned, namely airport policies in preventing acts of terrorism committed by airport visitors.

Conclusions, Recommendations and Limitations

The *perang semesta* strategy implemented in the Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport area, as an act of preventing acts of terrorism, is carried out by involving all components in the region. Human resources including airport personnel, policymakers, local governments where the airport is located, law enforcement officers, and TNI personnel who are at Sultan Hasanuddin Airport. Even though the airport is far from residential areas, aspects of the general public also become one of the considerations, considering that threats can come from anywhere by anyone since the strategy used is *semesta* (total/universal).

In the *perang semesta* strategy, in terms of preventing terrorism acts in the Sultan Hasanuddin Airport area, the actors involved are the Regional Government as the policymaker relating to the area where the airport is located and policymakers related to counseling related to the dangers of radicalism and terrorism to the community. The police, especially Counterterrorism Special Detachment 88 (Densus88) as actors to deal with acts of terror. The Indonesian National Army as a military, which one of its duties in Military Operations Apart from War is to assist the police in tackling acts of terrorism. Intelligence members from Indonesia Intelligence Agency (BIN), Police, and Indonesian National Army to carry out early detection so that early prevention can be carried out. Media as a channel of information to the entire community which is used in counseling and disseminating information about the dangers of terrorism. PT Angkasa Pura I as the policy maker in the Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport area. As well as people in South Sulawesi Province, especially in Makassar.

Prevention is carried out in this *perang semesta* strategy by means of preventive action because there has never been an act of terrorism at Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport before. Preventive action can be developed from various sources that also have the potential for preventive-effects, for example the press / mass media, the use of technological advances and the utilization of the potential preventive-effects of law enforcement officials such as raids/operations, educative communicative activities with the community, and so on. This is regulated in Government Regulation Number 77 of 2019, as follows: In the general public who, (1) have not been exposed to radicalism but have the potential to be exposed, (2) are classified as sympathizers, namely people who have a sense of sympathy but are still passive towards acts of radicalism and terrorism, (3) are having access to radical information, (4) are having a relationship with radical / terrorist elements, (5) are having a national spirit and a low economic level, and a culture that is easily exposed to radicalism (Santoso, Anwar, Waluyo, 2020).

Recommendations that can be offered in order to anticipate the potential threat of terrorism at Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport to enhance civil-military cooperation are:

- a. Carrying out continuous and integrated personnel development to minimize the potential threat of terrorism from insider factors.
- b. Upgrade and equip security equipment to increase the ability to anticipate threats of terrorism.
- c. Develop synergy with Sultan Hasanuddin Airport, especially in counterterrorism threat training at airports in accordance with the existing procedures.
- d. Maximizing the use of the media in an effort to minimize the increase in acts of terror that originate from radicalism.
- e. Maximizing the role of local clerics and traditional leaders in counter-radicalization, approaches to communities that tend to be radical so that this understanding does not develop into acts of terrorism.

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Appendix 1: Regulations and Laws

Peraturan Pemerintah Republik Indonesia Nomor 70 Tahun 2001 tentang Kebandarudaraan

Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 77 Tahun 2019 Tentang Pencegahan Tindak Pidana Terorisme dan Perlindungan terhadap Penyidik, Penuntut Umum, Hakim, dan Petugas Pemasyarakatan.

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